

A SIMPLIFIED MODEL FOR ANALYING LOW-VELOCITY IMPACT PROCESS OF COMPOSITE PLATES

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SUMMARY: A simplified model was developed which takes effect of indentation into account and can give the history of impact force、 displacement of a plates and impact durations during impact progress. The results from the developed model and finite element model were compared, and the application range of this model was discussed.

KEYWORDS: low velocity impact process, impact contact force, impact duration.

INTRODUCTION

Nowadays, composite materials are being largely used in the aerospace industry, either in structural elements or in fuselage parts. The laminated fiber-reinforced composite plates are known to be susceptible to damage resulting from accident impact of foreign objects. Such as the impact of a stone threw by the tires of a plane during landing or the drop of a handing tool. Although these impacts can occur without externally damaging the material, but their long term effect can't be disregarded. Delamination , fiber and /or matrix breakage and interface rupture are internal flaws that can occur under low energy impact event^[1].

Many works have been done in this field^[2], but no simple way can easily analyse the impact process .Dynamic finite element method is widely used in the analysis of low-velocity impact process of composite plates. This method is applicable widely and the results are accurate, but the preparation of data is complex , calculation time is long and the effects of the parameters in the impact process can't be measured easily.The goal of this work is to develop a simple model to analyse this process and give a way to measure the dynamic effects of the composite plates. Our paper developed a simplified model which takes indentation into account and can give the history of impact force and displacement of the plates during impact. We also compare the results from the developed model and finite element model,discuss the application range of this model and give a way to measure dynamic effects of the composite plates.

THE FOUNDATION AND APPLICATION OF THIS MODEL

Firstly the impact problems are simplified as follow:

- (1) During impact, the deformation of the plate、 stress and strain inside the plate can be treated as quasi-static state.
- (2) The impactor is rigid body, its mass is much bigger than that of the plate.
- (3) Impact force is in direct proportion to the indentation
- (4) The plates are linear elastic.

(5) The impactor and plates compose an energy conservation system, impact energy is fully converted to the plate deformation energy when the plate deformation reaches its maximum.

Base on these hypotheses, we can get equations bellows.

$$F = K_p \delta_p$$

(1)

$$F = K_i \alpha$$

(2)

$$F = \ddot{\delta} m$$

(3)

where F is contact force, K_p 、 K_i are plates flexural stiffness and linear contact parameter respectively, m is the mass of impactor, δ_p 、 α 、 δ is the flexural displacement 、indentation and the displacement of impactor. (figure 1) , they have the relations below:

$$\delta = \delta_p + \alpha$$

(4)

Fig.1 Contact condition between impactor and plates

By substituting equation(1), (2), (3) into equation(4), we can have:

$$\ddot{\delta} m + \delta \left(\frac{K_p K_i}{K_p + K_i} \right) = 0 \quad (5)$$

$\frac{K_p K_i}{K_p + K_i}$ can be look as elastic parameter of the system consists of the impactor and plates. equation(5) is the dynamic equation of impactor and subject to vibration law of single degree of freedom without damping.. so,when impact energy is E_0 , The impactor vibration period and the maximum value of impact force are:

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{\frac{m(K_p + K_i)}{K_p K_i}} \quad (6)$$

$$F_{\max} = \sqrt{\frac{2E_0 K_p K_i}{K_p + K_i}} \quad (7)$$

From equation (6), we know when $t \geq T/2$, $F \leq 0$, impact process is over, so The impact duration T_d is just the half of the vibration period:

$$T_d = \pi \sqrt{\frac{m(K_p + K_i)}{K_p K_i}} \quad (8)$$

The variation of impact force with time and flexural displacement of the plate are:

$$F = F_{\max} * \sin\left(\frac{2\pi t}{T}\right) \quad (9)$$

$$F = \left(\frac{K_p K_i}{K_p + K_i}\right) \delta \quad (10)$$

The variation of flexural displacement of the plate with time and its maximum value are:

$$\delta = \sqrt{\frac{2E_0 K_p K_i}{K_p + K_i}} \sin\left(\frac{\pi t}{T}\right) \quad (11)$$

$$\delta_{\max} = \sqrt{\frac{2E_0 K_p K_i}{K_p + K_i}} \quad (12)$$

equation (7) and (12) show: when plates elasticity and linear contact parameter are certain, impact duration is in direct proportion with square root of the impactor mass. Contact force and flexural displacement varies as sine function regulation and the max value is in direct proportion to square root of the impactor mass; contact force is in direct proportion to the flexural displacement

In order to use this model in the impact process. We must calculate the value of the parameter of K_p and K_i .

According to the paper^[3], the value K_p is only the 10 percent of K_i , so K_i is the major factor effecting the impact force.

According to the paper^[4]

$$F = K\alpha^{1.5} \quad (13)$$

F is the impact force, K is the contact parameter, we can get it from experience or calculated from equation below:

$$K = \frac{4}{3} \sqrt{r} \left[\frac{1}{(1 - r_s^2 / E_s + 1 / E_t)} \right] \quad (14)$$

r is the radius of impactor, r_s, E_s are poisson and elasticity module of the impactor material respectively. E_t is the across elasticity module of composite plate.

When max impact force is certain, the max indentation is also certain:

$$F_{\max} = Ki \alpha_{\max} = K \alpha_{\max} \quad (15)$$

$$Ki = \frac{K \alpha_{\max}}{\alpha_{\max}} = K^{\frac{2}{3}} F_{\max}^{\frac{1}{3}} \quad (16)$$

we can know the Ki is related with the value of maximum contact force by the impact. First, we obtained a static load-displacement curve through experimental static test^[5]. Then we need to integrate area under the curve until the integrated area has the same value as initial kinetic energy of impactor. The maximum force in the integrated area is the prediction maximum contact force by this way.

Now, we get the value of the Ki and all the parameters for the model are obtained.

Figure 2 and figure3 show the results from the model are correlated well with that of FEM for an impact of a T300/QY8911 composite plate which has a layout of [(45/0/-45/90)s]4, and dimension of 126mmx76mmx3.76mm^[4]. In the calculation Ki is 1.88×10^7 N/m calculated from equation(16). The results show clearly these two results fits each well.

Fig.2 History of Impact force

Fig.3 Impact force vs. flexural displacement of plate

APPLICABILITY ANALYSIS

The model developed above doesn't take the dynamic effects into account, but the dynamic effects can not be omitted in some impact event. when this influence is remarkable, impact contact force curve will appear the violent motion phenomenon, This will be made the great error in the calculation in this model, even give a wrong result. How can we measure the dynamic effects on the plates in the impact process. from literature^[3]we can know: the ratio R from impact duration and the period of the second vibration of a simply supported plate at four edges. ie:the number of vibration in the impact process is a important index,:

$$R = \frac{T_d}{T_2} \quad (17)$$

we will discuss all factors which effect the R value:

$$T_2 = \frac{2}{\pi} \left(\frac{a^2 b^2}{a^2 + b^2} \right) \sqrt{\frac{\rho h}{D}} \quad (18)$$

where a, b, h is the plates length, width and thickness respectively. ρ is mass density of plates, D is just for the bending stiffness of the plates.

By satisfying the assumption of this model, impact duration can be determined by

equation (8), if $K' = \sqrt{\frac{K_p + K_i}{K_i}}$, equation(12) can be rewrited as:

$$T_d = K' \pi \sqrt{\frac{m}{K_p}} \quad (19)$$

from literature^[6]:

$$K_p = \left[\sum_{i=1,3,5}^m \sum_{j=1,3,5}^m \frac{4}{D \pi^2 ab \left(\frac{i^2}{a^2} + \frac{j^2}{b^2} \right)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (20)$$

By substituting (14),(16) into (13),and $d = \frac{a}{b}$, we can get:

$$R = K' \sqrt{\frac{m}{abh\rho}} \left[\frac{1+4d^2}{d^2} \sum_{i=1,3,5}^m \sum_{j=1,3,5}^m \frac{1}{\left(i^2 + \frac{j^2}{b^2} \right)^2} \right]^{\frac{1}{2}} \quad (21)$$

general speaking ,because K_i is much bigger than K_p to plates. Variety scope of K' is small.when d is between 1/3 and 1,the value in the brace is between 1.6 and 2.6, Variety scope is also small,so the main factor that effects R is the ratio of impactor to the plates mass, when the ratio is bigger,we can get bigger value and get the accurate result from this model. This is in accordance with the hypothesis. It should be noted that R value has nothing to do with the impact energy and impact velocity.In addition, Because of the flexibility constant of the plate, such as E, G, ν etc only pass R to affect to the value E , they have little effect on R value.

Table (2)are the results calculated from the equation(21) and FEM for the steal plates. Therefore both results are coincidence. Table 1 give the calculation results calculated by the equation (21) and the FEM to for the composite plates, both results are also coincidence. This demonstrated that though equation (21) is deduced by isotropic plates. As the

material constant has little effect on R value, it also adapted the impact process calculation of quasi-isotropic composite plates.

Table 1 Impact force, Impact duration and R calculated from the model and FEM

Impact energy / J		5	17.8	26.7
Impact velocity / (m/s)		4.614	1.414	2.668
impactor / kg		0.4726	5.	5.
The max contact force F (N)	Model	4949.	4949.	9338.
	FEM	5523.	5151	9871
	Error%	10.4%	3.9%	5.4%
indentation δ_{max} (mm)	Model	1.92	1.92	3.63
	FEM	2.04	2.06	3.78
	Error%	5.6%	6.5%	3.9%
Impact duration Td (μ s)	Model	1380.	4488.	4488.
	FEM	1431.	4445.	4370.
	Error%	3.6%	-0.97%	-2.7%
R value (Td/T2)	Model	5.95	19.34	19.34
	FEM	7-	20-	20+

Note: the +(-) symbol attaching R demonstrated the actual value is big or small than this value, but is closest to the value.

Table 2 R for steel plate calculated from the model and FEM

Index	The size of steel plates / mm			impactor / kg	Impact energy / J	R value	
	length	width	thickness			model	FEM
1	125	75	4	5	5	8.68	9+
2	125	75	4	5	250	8.68	9+
3	125	200	3	20	20	8.04	9+

Note: the meaning of +,- is similar as Table 1.

The values in table 1 and table 2 are calculated with R value is greater than 7. In this condition, calculation results of simplified model are approximate with the calculation results of the FEM, But when the R value is smaller, such as for 1.2, the results from (7)(11)and(12) has a error even amount to 30% . So, when the R value is smaller, this simplified model has lost its value. When using this model, R value can be determined by conditions. According to the calculation result from literature^[3], when the R value is larger than 7, the results getting from simplified model have error less than 10% compared with the results getting from FEM.

CONCLUSION

The impact by the big mass impactor is very important in the problem of low-velocity impact process of composite plates, because the impact by the small impactor usually has lower energy. It is not easy to cause critical damage. Therefore, the low-velocity impact

research and the impact standard for composites aim at big mass impactor ,equal to the circumstance that impactor weighs about 5 Kgs where the R value is roughly same as 20.This condition is in the suitable use scope of this simplified model. Therefore, under the situation of not accounting the impact damage, this model can give a accurate result.

For the big energy impact , because the exist of the damage, equation(3),(4),(5) etc. all can't be established, the calculation results from the model have much error with the experiment results. But its calculation result have some value to the research of impact damage of composite plates.

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